

Methods for Determining Electrostatic Potential: A Computational Viewpoint

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Abstract

The learning outcomes are different for the courses taught at the physics undergraduate programs at the university level because of the prerequisites. Besides, the determination of the electrostatic potential is part of the physics curricula taught at the university's undergraduate or graduate physics degrees. The concept is necessary for a high level of mathematics; therefore, the difficulty in acquiring the desired outcome knowledge can be different for the students of physics undergraduate programs at the universities. The need to balance the mathematical skills necessary to understand materials has increased efforts in designing syllabuses with a gradual development and implementation of modern physics courses in curricula.

In this paper, I discuss a computational framework that can be established in the syllabuses of physics courses for determination of the electrostatic potential, at different levels of undergraduate and graduate university curricula aiming for a gradual transition from the university to the careers in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics.

Keywords

Electrostatic Potential, Method of Images, Laplace Equation, Poisson-Boltzmann Equation, Finite Difference Method

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of curricula that gradually implement new skills in learning physics is one of the main focuses of teaching the physical sciences¹. These curricula are meant to develop students' scientific and critical thinking; besides, the curricula should strengthen the students' interests and affinities for scientific reasoning and research^{2,3,4,5}.

Furthermore, the teaching methodology should include a variety of supportive learning techniques in the classroom (such as scientific reading materials, data structures, tables and graphs, videos, interactive discussion, animations, and software) combined with a problem- and project-based learning strategies^{3,4,5,6}, including Augmented Reality (AR)⁷ and Artificial Intelligence (AI)⁸.

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More importantly, the students should be prepared to identify the physical quantities and to measure and identify trends in the user data utilising data processing tools and graphics⁹. That helps develop students' problem-solving skills, collaborative and group learning skills, and thinking; furthermore, it allows the students to be independent. Introduction of the modern physics courses at the undergraduate and graduate university programs has attracted many students to the physical sciences courses; however, the need to balance the mathematical and computational skills necessary to gain an understanding of materials has increased efforts in designing teaching methodologies with a gradual development and implementation of such courses in curricula.

In our previous work^{10,11} and others^{12,13,14}, it is aimed to develop reading materials on the fundamental concepts of physics and how different theories developed from physical observations and phenomena, geared more towards examples and problem-solving techniques. The students get a firsthand experience of how physics theories are applied to engineering and science problems and were mainly aimed at the undergraduate and graduate students in engineering and science.

This study aims to create an in-class material to balance the mathematical and computational skills necessary to understand the reading material. In particular, methods for determining the electrostatic potential are part of any curriculum in science and engineering that include courses in electromagnetism or electrostatics, which is also the focus here.

II. THE METHOD OF IMAGES

The electric field produced by a known distribution of charges can be calculated in simple cases, by the application of Gauss's Law and the principle of superposition^{15,16}. Often, however, the charge is unknown and the problem can be solved by the use of Gauss's law by making assumptions about the distribution of charges from the symmetry of the problem^{13,12,11}.

Consider an uncharged and isolated conducting sheet. If we place it in an external uniform electric field (\mathbf{E}_0), then equal positive and negative charges are induced on the conducting sheet, as shown in Figure 1(a). The currents flow in the plane of the sheet (see Figure 1(a)); the electric field pattern is changed (that is, there is an induced electric field in the opposite direction and with the same magnitude, $-\mathbf{E}_0$) so that the total electric field in the plane of the sheet is $\mathbf{E} = 0$. Thus, the sheet becomes an equipotential surface $V_A = V_B$, as shown in Figure 1(b).

When the sheet is placed perpendicular to the direction of the external uniform electric field \mathbf{E}_0 , then it coincides with an equipotential surface, as illustrated in Figure 2. The direction of current flow is perpendicular to the plane of the sheet and the two surfaces become oppositely charged (see also Figure 2). If the sheet is thin, the separation of the positive and negative charges is small and the electric field pattern does not change by the presence of the conducting sheet.

This fact can be used to extend the range of problems which can be solved by elementary methods¹⁷.

For example¹², a conducting sheet can be placed along the equipotential AB (or CD) in Figure 3. It screens the two charges from each other; thus, either could be removed without affecting the field pattern on the other charge on the opposite side of the sheet. Thus the field pattern between one of the charges and a conducting plane is just half of that of a pair of oppositely charges. The same experiment can be conducted using two or four charged wires, as illustrated in Ref.¹².

The field between a charge and a conducting plane can also be found in the following^{15,12,17}. Figure 3 indicates that an image charge can be placed on the opposite side of the plane to produce an electric field

Fig. 1. (a) An uncharged and isolated conducting sheet placed in an external uniform electric field \mathbf{E}_0 along the plane of the sheet. (b) Illustration of how the conducting sheet becomes an equipotential surface.

Fig. 2. A thin uncharged and isolated conducting sheet placed in an external uniform electric field \mathbf{E}_0 perpendicular to the plane of the sheet.

pattern which is the mirror image of the original electric field. The so-called image charge is equal in magnitude to the original charge and opposite sign (see also Figure 3). The plane becomes an equipotential surface in the electric field of the two charges (as in Figure 3(a)) or four charges (as in Figure 3(b)); thus, removing it does not alter the electric field pattern. Therefore, the problem reduces to the superposition of the electric fields of the original and image charges, as presented in Figure 3. This method is known as the *method of images*, and it is also discussed previously¹⁷. The method of images applies to the solution of the problems involving charges and conducting surfaces if a set of image charges can be found such that the equipotentials in free space of the whole set of charges coincide with the conducting boundaries (see Refs.^{15,16,12} for more details).

Fig. 3. The electric field lines created by (Top) two charges of opposite sign where AB represents an equipotential surface; and (Bottom) four charges of opposite sign where AB and CD represent the equipotential surfaces.

A. Case Study: Grounded Spherical Conductor

For an illustration of the basics of method of images for the grounded and non-grounded spherical conductors, see A and A, respectively.

Figure 4 presents an interactive simulation of the potential V_P within a sphere of radius $r = 15$ cm and origin at O . We projected V_p on a plane along the z -axis taken along d such that for a fixed z , $V_P(x, y)$. For numerical purposes, a positive point charge $q = +1 \mu\text{C}$ is placed at a distance $d = 10$ cm from a grounded spherical conductor with radius of $a = 5$ cm. There are 41 slides along z -axis, where each step is $dz = r/20 = 0.75$ cm and $z \in [-r, r]$ such that $z = r - k \cdot dz$. Figure 4 shows $V_p(x, y)$ at the slider position of $k = 20$, or equivalently $z = 0$ cm from the origin O . It can be seen that there is an electric potential difference between two points along x -axis, which disappears for other positions of the slider.

A computer program is developed to perform an interactive simulation of the induced charge distribution of a positive point charge q placed close to a grounded spherical conductor at a distance $d = 11.4$ cm, as presented in Figure 5. For numerical calculations: $q = +1 \mu\text{C}$; $a = 1$ cm. Dark blue colour indicates a high negative charge density and light gray a zero charge density. The red sphere represents the real positive charge and the blue sphere represents the image charge.

Furthermore, Figure 6 shows an interactive simulation of the induced charge distribution as a function of the polar angle θ . A positive point charge q is placed close to a grounded spherical conductor at a distance d . Here, $q = +1 \mu\text{C}$ and the radius of the sphere is $a = 1$ cm.

The force between charge and sphere is calculate using the Coulomb's law:

$$F = k_e \frac{qq_1}{(d - d_1)^2} \tag{1}$$

Fig. 4. Interactive simulation of the potential V_P within a sphere of radius $r = 15$ cm and origin at O , projected on a plane along the z -axis taken along d , of a positive point charge $q = +1 \mu C$ placed at a distance $d = 10$ cm from a grounded spherical conductor with radius of $a = 5$ cm. The potential is projected on a plane perpendicular to z axis; There are 41 slides along z -axis, where each step is $dz = r/20 = 0.75$ cm and $z \in [-r, r]$ such that $z = r - k \cdot dz$. Here, we show $V_p(x, y)$ at the slider position of $k = 20$, or equivalently $z = 0$ cm from the origin O .

Fig. 5. Interactive simulation of the induced charge distribution of a positive point charge q placed close to a grounded spherical conductor at a distance d . For numerical calculations: $q = +1 \mu C$; $a = 1$ cm. Dark blue colour indicates a high negative charge density and light gray a zero charge density. The red sphere represents the real positive charge and the blue sphere represents the image charge.

Fig. 6. Interactive simulation of the induced charge density (in C/m^2) distribution of a positive point charge q placed close to a grounded spherical conductor at a distance d (in cm) as a function of the angle θ (in radians) from the line joining real and imaginary charge. For numerical calculations: $q = +1 \mu C$; $a = 1$ cm.

Replacing $q_1 = -aq/d$ and $d_1 = a^2/d$, we obtain

$$F = -k_e \frac{\frac{q^2 a}{d}}{\left(d - \frac{a^2}{d}\right)^2} = -k_e \frac{q^2 a d}{(d^2 - a^2)^2} \tag{2}$$

Here, the minus sign indicates that it is an attractive force. In Figure 7(a), we plot the force between a positive charge $q = +1.0 \mu C$ and a conducting sphere of different radius a (in centimetres) versus $(d - a)$. Similarly, in Figure 7(b), for the pressure applied in the conducting sphere.

Fig. 7. Interactive simulations: (a) The force between a positive charge $q = +1.0 \mu C$ and a conducting sphere of different radius a (in centimetres). (b) Similarly for the pressure applied in the conducting sphere.

B. Case Study: Non-grounded Spherical Conductor

An interactive simulation of the potential V_P at a point P at distance $r = 15$ cm from O of a positive point charge q placed close to a non-grounded spherical conductor at a distance d is shown in Figure 8. For numerical calculations: $q = +5 \mu C$; $a = 5$ cm.

Fig. 8. Interactive simulation of the potential V_P at a point P at distance $r = 15$ cm from O of a positive point charge q placed close to a non-grounded spherical conductor at a distance d . For numerical calculations: $q = +5 \mu\text{C}$; $a = 5$ cm.

III. CASE STUDIES: LAPLACE'S AND POISSON'S EQUATIONS

The theory of the Laplace's and Poisson's equations is presented in A.

1) *Example 1:* The potential $V_0(\theta)$ is specified on the surface of a hollow sphere, of radius R^{12} . Find the potential inside the sphere.

From the solution

$$V(r, \theta) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \left(A_l r^l + \frac{B_l}{r^{l+1}} \right) P_l(\cos \theta) \quad (3)$$

we can see that $B_l = 0, \forall l$, since V has to be finite for $r = 0$. Thus

$$V(r, \theta) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} A_l r^l P_l(\cos \theta) \quad (4)$$

Using the boundary conditions at $r = R$:

$$V(R, \theta) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} A_l R^l P_l(\cos \theta) = V_0(\theta) \quad (5)$$

Multiplying both sides by $P_{l'}(\cos \theta) \sin \theta$ and integrating:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^{\pi} P_{l'}(\cos \theta) \sin \theta V_0(\theta) d\theta \\ &= \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} A_l R^l \int_0^{\pi} P_{l'}(\cos \theta) \sin \theta P_l(\cos \theta) d\theta \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Using the orthogonality of polynomial Legendre functions¹⁸:

$$\int_0^{\pi} P_{l'}(\cos \theta) \sin \theta P_l(\cos \theta) d\theta = \frac{2}{2l+1} \delta_{ll'} \quad (7)$$

we obtain

$$\int_0^\pi P_{l'}(\cos \theta) \sin \theta V_0(\theta) d\theta = A_{l'} R^{l'} \frac{2}{2l' + 1} \tag{8}$$

or

$$A_l = \frac{2l + 1}{2R^l} \int_0^\pi P_l(\cos \theta) \sin \theta V_0(\theta) d\theta \tag{9}$$

Figure 9 presents an interactive simulation of the potential $V(r, \theta)$ mapped on the surface of an inner sphere created by a hollow sphere under a surface potential $V_0(\theta) = 0.5 + 1.5 \cos(0.3\theta) + 0.5 \sin(2.0\theta)$ and radius $R = 4$ units.

Fig. 9. Interactive simulation of the potential $V(r, \theta)$ mapped on the surface of an inner sphere created by a hollow sphere under a surface potential $V_0(\theta) = 0.5 + 1.5 \cos(0.3\theta) + 0.5 \sin(2.0\theta)$ and radius $R = 4$ units.

2) *Example 2:* The potential $V_0(\theta)$ is specified on the surface of a hollow sphere, of radius R^{12} . Find the potential outside the sphere.

From the solution

$$V(r, \theta) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \left(A_l r^l + \frac{B_l}{r^{l+1}} \right) P_l(\cos \theta) \tag{10}$$

we can see that $A_l = 0, \forall l$, since V has to be zero for $r = \infty$. Thus

$$V(r, \theta) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_l}{r^{l+1}} P_l(\cos \theta) \tag{11}$$

Using the boundary conditions at $r = R$:

$$V(R, \theta) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_l}{R^{l+1}} P_l(\cos \theta) = V_0(\theta) \tag{12}$$

Multiplying both sides by $P_{l'}(\cos \theta) \sin \theta$ and integrating:

$$\int_0^\pi P_{l'}(\cos \theta) \sin \theta V_0(\theta) d\theta = \sum_{l=0}^\infty \frac{B_l}{r^{l+1}} \int_0^\pi P_{l'}(\cos \theta) \sin \theta P_l(\cos \theta) d\theta \tag{13}$$

Using the orthogonality of polynomial Legendre functions:

$$\int_0^\pi P_{l'}(\cos \theta) \sin \theta P_l(\cos \theta) d\theta = \frac{2}{2l+1} \delta_{ll'} \tag{14}$$

we obtain

$$\int_0^\pi P_{l'}(\cos \theta) \sin \theta V_0(\theta) d\theta = \frac{B_{l'}}{r^{l'+1}} \frac{2}{2l'+1} \tag{15}$$

or

$$B_l = \frac{2l+1}{2} R^{l+1} \int_0^\pi P_l(\cos \theta) \sin \theta V_0(\theta) d\theta \tag{16}$$

Figure 10 illustrates the interactive simulation of the potential $V(r, \theta)$ mapped on the surface of an outer sphere created by a hollow sphere under a surface potential $V_0(\theta) = 0.5 + 1.5 \cos(0.3\theta) + 0.5 \sin(2.0\theta)$ and radius $R = 4$ units.

Fig. 10. Interactive simulation of the potential $V(r, \theta)$ mapped on the surface of an outer sphere created by a hollow sphere under a surface potential $V_0(\theta) = 0.5 + 1.5 \cos(0.3\theta) + 0.5 \sin(2.0\theta)$ and radius $R = 4$ units.

IV. CASE STUDY: GREEN'S THEOREM

Green's theorem is described in B3.

A. Example

Consider a sphere with radius a which is grounded and at distance d from the centre of the sphere there is a charge q . Find the induced charge on the sphere¹².

In the first state, we can determine:

$$\begin{aligned} q_1 &= q; & V_1 &= V_s(q) \\ q_2 &= q_1; & V_2 &= V_s(a) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where $V_s(q)$ and $V_s(a)$ are the potential created by the induced sphere at point where charge q is placed and at the surface of sphere, respectively. q_1 is the charge induced to the sphere.

Now, consider that we remove the contact with the ground, and let q_2 be the charge induced to the sphere. Then, the second state is:

$$\begin{aligned} q'_1 &= 0; & V'_1 &= k_e \frac{q_2}{d} \\ q'_2 &= q_2; & V'_2 &= k_e \frac{q_2}{a} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where q'_1 is the charge inside sphere.

Using the Green's theorem

$$q_1 k_e \frac{q_2}{d} + q_2 k_e \frac{q_2}{a} = q'_1 V_a(q) + q'_2 V_s(a) \quad (19)$$

or

$$q k_e \frac{q_2}{d} + q_1 k_e \frac{q_2}{a} = 0 \cdot V_a(q) + q_2 \cdot 0 = 0 \quad (20)$$

Thus,

$$q_1 = -q \frac{a}{d} \quad (21)$$

V. CASE STUDY: THE FINITE DIFFERENCE METHOD

The Poisson-Boltzmann equation and the finite difference method are described in B3.

A. Example – Molecular Electrostatic Potential

All the molecules used in this study are designed by a modified version of MolView software¹⁹ implemented in Ref.²⁰. The geometries are optimised using quantum mechanics at the Hartree-Fock level with PySCF package²¹, as implemented in Ref.²⁰, using 6-31+G** basis set²².

Figure 11 shows the molecular electrostatic potential of a molecule²³ mapped on the molecule surface and its partial atomic charges according a colour scaling. The molecular electrostatic potential is computed using Jmol software²⁴ as implemented in Ref.²⁰.

The second example is (2S)-2-chlorobutane molecule²⁵ for which the electrostatic potential volumetric map and isosurface of the electrostatic potential are calculated using the PMEpot plugin for calculation of the electrostatic potential grid²⁶. The partial atomic charges calculated based on the molecular mechanics

Fig. 11. The molecular electrostatic potential of a molecule ($C_{16}H_{14}N_2O_5$)²³ and its partial atomic charges calculated based on the molecular mechanics force fields are shown for each atom according to a colour scale. Jmol software²⁴ was used for calculations as implemented in Reference²⁰.

force fields²⁷ using a colour scale (blue: positive charge and red: negative charge). The vmd software²⁸ was used for visualisations. Figure 12 shows the electrostatic potential mapped in a three-dimensional grid and the three volume slices corresponding to the planes with $X = 0$, $Y = 0$, and $Z = 0$, respectively, coloured according to the scheme: blue: electrostatic potential $V > 0$, gray: $V = 0$, and red: $V < 0$. Besides, the isosurfaces are shown at three different values of the electrostatic potential $V < 0$, $V = 0$ (equipotential isosurfaces), and $V > 0$, respectively, as depicted in Figure 12.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study discusses a pedagogical framework that can be established in the syllabuses of physics courses of the electromagnetism and electrodynamics on the methods for determining the electrostatic potential at the undergraduate and graduate university curricula. This study aims to gradually transition from university to careers in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics.

In particular, it aims to create an in-class material by balancing the mathematical and computational skills necessary to gain an understanding of modern physics concepts, hence creating a teaching material that focuses on coaching a self-directed curiosity on real-world issues and, at the same time, encouraging social interaction in the process of learning^{29,30}.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I am grateful to the International Balkan University students of Electrical and Electronic Engineering (classes 2014-2018 and 2015-2019) for many fruitful discussions during the Theory of Electromagnetism lectures.

APPENDIX

To illustrate the basics of method of images we are going to consider the problem of finding the electric field created from a positive point charge q placed close to a spherical conductor, which is grounded, shown in Figure 13, discussed widely in the literature^{15,12}. The primary goal is to develop an interactive computer simulation of the problem using the computation models. The *image charge* (fictitious charge)

Fig. 12. The molecular electrostatic potential of (2S)-2-chlorobutane molecule²⁵ and its partial atomic charges calculated based on the molecular mechanics force fields²⁷ are shown for each atom according to a colour scale (blue: positive charge and red: negative charge). The vmd software²⁸ was used for visualisation and the PMEpot plugin for calculation of the electrostatic potential grid²⁶.

q_1 is at distance d_1 from the centre of sphere. Let P be a point on the surface of sphere, then the electric potential at P is

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_P &= k_e \left(\frac{q}{r} + \frac{q_1}{r_1} \right) \\
 &= k_e \left(\frac{q}{|\mathbf{d} + \mathbf{a}|} + \frac{q_1}{|\mathbf{d}_1 + \mathbf{a}|} \right) \\
 &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

where $\mathbf{d} = d\mathbf{d}_0$, $\mathbf{d}_1 = d_1\mathbf{d}_0$ and $\mathbf{a} = a\mathbf{n}$. Thus,

$$V_P = 0 = k_e \left(\frac{q}{|d\mathbf{d}_0 + a\mathbf{n}|} + \frac{q_1}{|d_1\mathbf{d}_0 + a\mathbf{n}|} \right) \tag{23}$$

Fig. 13. Consider a positive point charge q placed close to a grounded spherical conductor.

We can write

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 &= V_P & (24) \\
 &= k_e \left(\frac{q}{\sqrt{d^2 + a^2 - 2ad \cos \theta}} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{q_1}{\sqrt{d_1^2 + a^2 - 2ad_1 \cos \theta}} \right) \\
 &= k_e \left(\frac{q}{d \sqrt{1 + \frac{a^2}{d^2} - 2\frac{a}{d} \cos \theta}} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{q_1}{a \sqrt{1 + \frac{d_1^2}{a^2} - 2\frac{d_1}{a} \cos \theta}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that Eq. (24) is satisfied for

$$\frac{q}{d} = -\frac{q_1}{a}; \quad \frac{a}{d} = \frac{d_1}{a}, \tag{25}$$

or,

$$q_1 = -\frac{a}{d}q; \quad d_1 = \frac{a^2}{d} \tag{26}$$

Thus, the potential at any point P outside the sphere is

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_P &= k_e q \left(\frac{1}{r_0} - \frac{a}{dr_1} \right) \\
 &= k_e q \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{d^2 + r^2 - 2rd \cos \theta}} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{a}{d\sqrt{r^2 + d_1^2 - 2rd_1 \cos \theta}} \right) \\
 &= k_e q \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{d^2 + r^2 - 2rd \cos \theta}} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{a}{d\sqrt{r^2 + \left(\frac{a^2}{d}\right)^2 - 2r\left(\frac{a^2}{d}\right) \cos \theta}} \right) \\
 &= \frac{k_e q}{d} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{r}{d}\right)^2 - 2\frac{r}{d} \cos \theta}} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{a}{d}\right)^2 - 2\frac{r}{d} \cos \theta}} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

Following^{15,12}, the surface charge density of induced charges in the surface of grounded sphere is

$$\sigma_P = \epsilon_0 E_P = -\epsilon_0 (\nabla_{\mathbf{r}} V_P)_{\text{outside sphere}} \tag{28}$$

since

$$(\nabla_{\mathbf{r}} V_P)_{\text{inside sphere}} = 0 \tag{29}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_P &= -k_e \epsilon_0 q \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{a}{dr_1} \right) \\
 &= -k_e \epsilon_0 \left[\left(\nabla_r \left(\frac{1}{r} \right) \right) \cdot \mathbf{n} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{\partial r_1}{\partial r} \left(\nabla_{r_1} \left(\frac{a}{dr_1} \right) \right) \cdot \mathbf{n} \right] \\
 &= -k_e \epsilon_0 \left(-\frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{n}}{r^3} + \frac{a^2}{d^2} \frac{\mathbf{r}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}}{r_1^3} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 \nabla \left(\frac{1}{r} \right) &= \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \mathbf{k} \right) \frac{1}{r} \\
 &= -\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial r}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial r}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial r}{\partial z} \mathbf{k} \\
 &= -\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{x}{r} \mathbf{i} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{y}{r} \mathbf{j} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{z}{r} \mathbf{k} = -\frac{\mathbf{r}}{r^3}
 \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

where $r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$, $\mathbf{r} = x\mathbf{i} + y\mathbf{j} + z\mathbf{k}$ and

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial r}{\partial x} &= \frac{x}{r}, & \frac{\partial r}{\partial y} &= \frac{y}{r}, \\ \frac{\partial r}{\partial z} &= \frac{z}{r}, & \frac{\partial r_1}{\partial r} &= \frac{a}{d}.\end{aligned}\quad (32)$$

We can further simplify the expression

$$\sigma_P = -k_e \epsilon_0 q \left(-\frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{n}}{r^3} + \frac{a^2 \mathbf{r}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}}{d^2 r_1^3} \right) \quad (33)$$

as follows (by replacing $d_1 = a^2/d$)

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_P &= -k_e \epsilon_0 q \left(-\frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{n}}{(d^2 + a^2 - 2ad \cos \theta)^{3/2}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{a^2}{d^2} \frac{\mathbf{r}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}}{(d_1^2 + a^2 - 2ad_1 \cos \theta)^{3/2}} \right) \\ &= -k_e \epsilon_0 q \left(-\frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{n}}{(d^2 + a^2 - 2ad \cos \theta)^{3/2}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\mathbf{r}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}}{(d^2 + a^2 - 2ad \cos \theta)^{3/2}} \right) \\ &= k_e \epsilon_0 \frac{(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_1) \cdot \mathbf{n}}{(d^2 + a^2 - 2ad \cos \theta)^{3/2}} \\ &= -k_e \epsilon_0 q \frac{(d - d_1) \cos \theta}{(d^2 + a^2 - 2ad \cos \theta)^{3/2}} \\ &= -k_e \epsilon_0 q \frac{(d^2 - a^2) \cos \theta}{d(d^2 + a^2 - 2ad \cos \theta)^{3/2}}\end{aligned}\quad (34)$$

Following^{15,12}, the surface charge density of induced charges in the surface of grounded sphere is

$$\sigma_P = \epsilon_0 E_P = -\epsilon_0 (\nabla_{\mathbf{r}} V_P)_{\text{outside sphere}} \quad (35)$$

since

$$(\nabla_{\mathbf{r}} V_P)_{\text{inside sphere}} = 0 \quad (36)$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_P &= -k_e \epsilon_0 q \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{a}{dr_1} \right) \\ &= -k_e \epsilon_0 \left[\left(\nabla_r \left(\frac{1}{r} \right) \right) \cdot \mathbf{n} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{\partial r_1}{\partial r} \left(\nabla_{r_1} \left(\frac{a}{dr_1} \right) \right) \cdot \mathbf{n} \right] \\ &= -k_e \epsilon_0 \left(-\frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{n}}{r^3} + \frac{a^2 \mathbf{r}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}}{d^2 r_1^3} \right)\end{aligned}\quad (37)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla\left(\frac{1}{r}\right) &= \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x}\mathbf{i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}\mathbf{j} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z}\mathbf{k}\right)\frac{1}{r} \\ &= -\frac{1}{r^2}\frac{\partial r}{\partial x}\mathbf{i} - \frac{1}{r^2}\frac{\partial r}{\partial y}\mathbf{j} - \frac{1}{r^2}\frac{\partial r}{\partial z}\mathbf{k} \\ &= -\frac{1}{r^2}\frac{x}{r}\mathbf{i} - \frac{1}{r^2}\frac{y}{r}\mathbf{j} - \frac{1}{r^2}\frac{z}{r}\mathbf{k} = -\frac{\mathbf{r}}{r^3}\end{aligned}\quad (38)$$

where $r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$, $\mathbf{r} = x\mathbf{i} + y\mathbf{j} + z\mathbf{k}$ and

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial r}{\partial x} &= \frac{x}{r}, & \frac{\partial r}{\partial y} &= \frac{y}{r}, \\ \frac{\partial r}{\partial z} &= \frac{z}{r}, & \frac{\partial r_1}{\partial r} &= \frac{a}{d}.\end{aligned}\quad (39)$$

We can further simplify the expression

$$\sigma_P = -k_e\epsilon_0q\left(-\frac{\mathbf{r}\cdot\mathbf{n}}{r^3} + \frac{a^2}{d^2}\frac{\mathbf{r}_1\cdot\mathbf{n}}{r_1^3}\right)\quad (40)$$

as follows (by replacing $d_1 = a^2/d$)

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_P &= -k_e\epsilon_0q\left(-\frac{\mathbf{r}\cdot\mathbf{n}}{(d^2 + a^2 - 2ad\cos\theta)^{3/2}}\right. \\ &\quad \left.+ \frac{a^2}{d^2}\frac{\mathbf{r}_1\cdot\mathbf{n}}{(d_1^2 + a^2 - 2ad_1\cos\theta)^{3/2}}\right) \\ &= -k_e\epsilon_0q\left(-\frac{\mathbf{r}\cdot\mathbf{n}}{(d^2 + a^2 - 2ad\cos\theta)^{3/2}}\right. \\ &\quad \left.+ \frac{\mathbf{r}_1\cdot\mathbf{n}}{(d^2 + a^2 - 2ad\cos\theta)^{3/2}}\right) \\ &= k_e\epsilon_0\frac{(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_1)\cdot\mathbf{n}}{(d^2 + a^2 - 2ad\cos\theta)^{3/2}} \\ &= -k_e\epsilon_0q\frac{(d - d_1)\cos\theta}{(d^2 + a^2 - 2ad\cos\theta)^{3/2}} \\ &= -k_e\epsilon_0q\frac{(d^2 - a^2)\cos\theta}{d(d^2 + a^2 - 2ad\cos\theta)^{3/2}}\end{aligned}\quad (41)$$

Consider now the case of spherical conductor which is not grounded, so that the electric potential at the surface is not zero, as shown in Figure 14. In this case of an isolated sphere in order to have the total charge equal to zero we should place at the centre of the sphere a charge $q_2 = -q_1$. In this way, the

electric potential is

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_p &= k_e \left(\frac{q}{r} + \frac{q_1}{r_1} + \frac{q_2}{r_P} \right) \\
 &= k_e \left(\frac{q}{r} + \frac{q_1}{r_1} - \frac{q_1}{r_P} \right) \\
 &= k_e \left(\frac{q}{r} + \frac{q_1}{r_1} - \frac{q_1}{r_P} \right) \\
 &= k_e \left(\frac{q}{|d\mathbf{d}_0 + r_P\mathbf{n}|} + \frac{q_1}{|d_1\mathbf{d}_0 + r_P\mathbf{n}|} - \frac{q_1}{r_P} \right) \\
 &= k_e \left(\frac{q}{d\sqrt{1 + \frac{r_P^2}{d^2} - 2\frac{r_P}{d}\cos\theta}} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{q_1}{r_P\sqrt{1 + \frac{d_1^2}{r_P^2} - 2\frac{d_1}{r_P}\cos\theta}} - \frac{q_1}{r_P} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

where r , r_1 , and r_P are the distances of charges q , q_1 and q_2 from the observation point P , respectively. Note that $V_p(r_P = a) \neq 0$ and $q_1 = -qa/d$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_p &= \frac{k_e q}{d} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{r_P^2}{d^2} - 2\frac{r_P}{d}\cos\theta}} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{a}{r_P\sqrt{1 + \frac{d_1^2}{r_P^2} - 2\frac{d_1}{r_P}\cos\theta}} + \frac{a}{r_P} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

If the spherical conductor has initially its own charge Q , then this would be replaced at the centre of sphere as well, in such case, the total charge at the centre becomes $\tilde{q}_2 = q_2 + Q$, and

$$V_p = k_e \left(\frac{q}{r} + \frac{q_1}{r_1} + \frac{\tilde{q}_2}{r_2} \right) \tag{44}$$

The method described in the previous section has been applied with ingenuity to a wide variety of problems whose solutions can be looked up when required.

A. The Differential Form of Gauss's Law

Only a limited range of problems can be solved by the direct use of Gauss's Law in the form^{15,12,11}:

$$\oint_S \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{A} = \frac{Q_{in}}{\epsilon_0} \tag{45}$$

Fig. 14. Consider a positive point charge q placed close to a non-grounded spherical conductor.

For a continuous charge distribution in a volume V , we have

$$Q_{in} = \int_V \rho dV \tag{46}$$

where ρ is volume charge density. Then,

$$\oint_S \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \int_V \rho dV \tag{47}$$

Another form, which is obtained by applying it to a small volume element, enables us to solve a much wider range of problems.

To calculate the net flux out of the element, consider first the two shaded faces A and B which are perpendicular to the x -axis. The only component of \mathbf{E} which contributes to the flux through these faces is E_x . If the component of \mathbf{E} is E_x on A then, in general, the x component of \mathbf{E} on B can be written:

$$E_x + dE_x = E_x + \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial x} dx \tag{48}$$

Provided that the dimensions of the element are small enough we can assume that these components are constant on the surfaces A and B. The flux of \mathbf{E} out of the volume through the faces A and B is then

$$-E_x dydz + \left(E_x + \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial x} dx \right) dydz = \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial x} dx dydz \tag{49}$$

The same argument can be used for the other two directions in space, with the result that the net flux of \mathbf{E} out of the element is

$$d\Phi_E = \left(\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial z} \right) dx dydz \tag{50}$$

Combining with Gauss's Law:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_E &= \int_V d\Phi_E = \int_V \left(\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial z} \right) dV \\ &= \frac{1}{\epsilon_0} \int_V \rho(x, y, z) dV \end{aligned} \tag{51}$$

where $dV = dx dydz$. Then, we obtain

$$\left(\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial z} \right) = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \tag{52}$$

Introducing the divergent operator in Cartesian coordinates:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial z} \quad (53)$$

we obtain

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (54)$$

where ∇ operator is given in Cartesian coordinates as:

$$\nabla = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \mathbf{k} \quad (55)$$

Using the equation:

$$\mathbf{E} = -\nabla V \quad (56)$$

We get

$$\nabla \cdot (-\nabla V) = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (57)$$

Or,

$$\nabla^2 V = -\frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (58)$$

This is known as *Poisson's equation*. It can also be written as

$$\Delta V = -\frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (59)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta &= \nabla^2 \\ &= \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \end{aligned} \quad (60)$$

When there is no free charge present the equation takes a simpler form known as Laplace's equation:

$$\Delta V = 0 \quad (61)$$

B. Solutions of Laplace's Equation

1) *Cartesian Coordinates*: Laplace's equation in Cartesian coordinates is^{15,12}:

$$\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (62)$$

We can require the solution in the form:

$$V(x, y, z) = X(x)Y(y)Z(z) \quad (63)$$

Then, we obtain

$$\frac{1}{X} \frac{d^2 X(x)}{dx^2} + \frac{1}{Y} \frac{d^2 Y(y)}{dy^2} + \frac{1}{Z} \frac{d^2 Z(z)}{dz^2} = 0 \quad (64)$$

For this to be satisfied, we have to have:

$$\frac{1}{X} \frac{d^2 X(x)}{dx^2} + \frac{1}{Y} \frac{d^2 Y(y)}{dy^2} = -\frac{1}{Z} \frac{d^2 Z(z)}{dz^2} = -k^2 \quad (65)$$

where k is a constant independent of coordinates. Then, we can denote:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{1}{X} \frac{d^2 X(x)}{dx^2} &= -\omega_1^2, \\ \frac{1}{Y} \frac{d^2 Y(y)}{dy^2} &= -\omega_2^2\end{aligned}\quad (66)$$

where ω_1 and ω_2 are two constants. For solving the last two equations, we have to solve an equation of the form:

$$\frac{d^2 X(x)}{dx^2} + \omega^2 X(x) = 0 \quad (67)$$

Require the solution in the form $X(x) = e^{\rho x}$ where ρ a constant:

$$\rho^2 e^{\rho x} + \omega^2 e^{\rho x} = 0 \quad (68)$$

or

$$\rho^2 + \omega^2 = 0 \rightarrow \rho_{1,2} = \pm i\omega \quad (69)$$

where $i = \sqrt{-1}$. Then, the solution is required as:

$$X(x) = Ae^{-i\omega x} + Be^{i\omega x} \quad (70)$$

Therefore, for $X(x)$ and $Y(y)$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}X(x) &= A_1 e^{-i\omega_1 x} + B_1 e^{i\omega_1 x} \\ Y(y) &= A_2 e^{-i\omega_2 y} + B_2 e^{i\omega_2 y}\end{aligned}$$

Next, we search for the solution of

$$\frac{d^2 Z(z)}{dz^2} - k^2 Z(z) = 0 \quad (71)$$

Require the solution in the form $Z(z) = e^{\rho z}$ where ρ a constant:

$$\rho^2 e^{\rho z} - k^2 e^{\rho z} = 0 \quad (72)$$

or

$$\rho^2 - k^2 = 0 \rightarrow \rho_{1,2} = \pm k \quad (73)$$

Then, the solution is required as:

$$Z(z) = A_3 e^{-kz} + B_3 e^{kz} \quad (74)$$

Therefore, for $Z(z)$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}Z(z) &= A_3 e^{-kz} + B_3 e^{kz} \\ &= A_3 e^{-\sqrt{\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2} z} + B_3 e^{\sqrt{\omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2} z}\end{aligned}\quad (75)$$

The constants ω_1 and ω_2 are determined from the boundary conditions, depending on the problem.

2) *Spherical Coordinates*: Cartesian coordinates are the choice for solving problems with boundary conditions *planes*. For *round* objects spherical coordinates are more natural. In spherical system, with axial symmetry ($V(r, \theta)$), Laplace's equation become^{15,12}

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial V}{\partial \theta} \right) = 0 \quad (76)$$

We are going to look for solutions in the form¹²

$$V(r, \theta) = R(r)\Theta(\theta) \quad (77)$$

Replace it in the previous equation, and get

$$\Theta(\theta) \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{dR}{dr} \right) + \frac{R(r)}{\sin \theta} \frac{d}{d\theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{d\Theta}{d\theta} \right) = 0 \quad (78)$$

Divide both sides by $V(r, \theta)$, we get

$$\frac{1}{R} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{dR}{dr} \right) + \frac{1}{\Theta \sin \theta} \frac{d}{d\theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{d\Theta}{d\theta} \right) = 0 \quad (79)$$

Since the first term depends only on r and second only on θ , we may write

$$\frac{1}{R} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{dR}{dr} \right) = l(l+1), \quad (80)$$

$$\frac{1}{\Theta \sin \theta} \frac{d}{d\theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{d\Theta}{d\theta} \right) = -l(l+1)$$

The first equation can be written as^{15,12}

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{dR}{dr} \right) = l(l+1)R(r) \quad (81)$$

This equation has a general solution of the form

$$R(r) = Ar^l + \frac{B}{r^{l+1}} \quad (82)$$

where A and B are two constants, determined from boundary conditions.

One may come faster to this guess by replacing: $R(r) = \xi(r)/r$:

$$\frac{d^2 \xi}{dr^2} = \frac{\xi}{r^2} l(l+1) \quad (83)$$

which has the solution in the form:

$$\xi(r) = Ar^{l+1} + B/r^l \quad (84)$$

where A and B are two constants.

The second equation can be written as

$$\frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{d}{d\theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{d\Theta}{d\theta} \right) = -l(l+1)\Theta(\theta) \quad (85)$$

By replacing $x = \cos \theta$, we obtain

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left((1-x^2) \frac{d\Theta}{dx} \right) + l(l+1)\Theta = 0 \quad (86)$$

This is known as Legendre Equation¹⁸, with a general solution of the form

$$\Theta(x) = P_l(x) \quad (87)$$

where $P_l(x)$ is the Legendre polynomial of order l .

Since it is required that $\Theta(\theta) = \Theta(\theta + 2\pi)$, for symmetry, then l has to be an integer number. Then, the general solution is required as

$$V(r, \theta) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \left(A_l r^l + \frac{B_l}{r^{l+1}} \right) P_l(\cos \theta) \quad (88)$$

where

$$P_0(x) = 1; P_1(x) = x; P_2(x) = \frac{1}{2}(3x^2 - 1) \quad (89)$$

where the Rodrigues formula can be used¹⁸:

$$P_l(x) = \frac{1}{2^l l!} \left(\frac{d}{dx} \right)^l (x^2 - 1)^l \quad (90)$$

3) *Cylindrical coordinates:* In Cylindrical coordinates (r, ϕ, z) , the Laplace's equation is^{15,12}

$$\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (91)$$

The electric potential $V(r, \phi, z)$ is required in the form

$$V(r, \phi, z) = R(r)Q(\phi)Z(z) \quad (92)$$

Replacing this expression into equation, we obtain

$$QZ \frac{\partial^2 R}{\partial r^2} + \frac{QZ}{r} \frac{\partial R}{\partial r} + \frac{RZ}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 Q}{\partial \phi^2} + RQ \frac{\partial^2 Z}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (93)$$

Dividing both sides by V , we get

$$\frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial^2 R}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{R r} \frac{\partial R}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{Q r^2} \frac{\partial^2 Q}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{1}{Z} \frac{\partial^2 Z}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (94)$$

Since each term depends only on one variable we can write:

$$\frac{1}{Q} \frac{d^2 Q}{d\phi^2} = -n^2 \quad (95)$$

$$\frac{1}{Z} \frac{d^2 Z}{dz^2} = m^2$$

$$\frac{1}{R} \frac{d^2 R}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{R r} \frac{dR}{dr} = - \left(m^2 - \frac{n^2}{r^2} \right)$$

or

$$\frac{d^2 Q}{d\phi^2} + n^2 Q = 0 \quad (96)$$

$$\frac{d^2 Z}{dz^2} - m^2 Z = 0$$

$$\frac{d^2 R}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{dR}{dr} + \left(m^2 - \frac{n^2}{r^2} \right) R = 0$$

where m and n are partition parameters. The solutions of the first two equations are given by (as discussed above):

$$\begin{aligned} Q(\phi) &= A_1 e^{-in\phi} + B_1 e^{in\phi} \\ Z(z) &= A_2 e^{-mz} + B_2 e^{mz} \end{aligned} \tag{97}$$

Assume that m is a real parameter, then denoting $x = mr$, we get

$$\frac{d^2 R}{dx^2} + \frac{1}{x} \frac{dR}{dx} + \left(1 - \frac{n^2}{x^2}\right) R = 0 \tag{98}$$

which is Bessel equation. Solution is the Bessel function of first type: $J_n(x)$ and $J_{-n}(x)$ for n integer number^{18,12}. These solutions are linearly independent, thus we can express the general solution as a linear combination of $J_n(x)$ and Neuman function $N_n(x)$ ¹⁸:

$$N_n(x) = \frac{J_n(x) \cos n\pi - J_{-n}(x)}{\sin n\pi} \tag{99}$$

Then,

$$R(r) = A_3 J_n(mr) + B_3 N_n(mr) \tag{100}$$

With help of the Green's theorem can be solved many problems in electrostatic¹⁵. Suppose that is given a system of charges q_1, q_2, \dots, q_N . Each charge q_j is placed at a point with potential V_j created from all other charges of system except the q_j ^{15,12}:

$$V_j = k_e \sum_{i=1 \neq j}^N \frac{q_i}{r_{ij}} \tag{101}$$

Suppose that at the same previous points, we place another set of charges q'_1, \dots, q'_N , then at the point j the potential is

$$V'_j = k_e \sum_{i=1 \neq j}^N \frac{q'_i}{r_{ij}} \tag{102}$$

Now, we multiply the first equation with q'_j and the second with q_j both sides and sum over all j :

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=1}^N V_j q'_j &= k_e \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{i=1 \neq j}^N \frac{q_i q'_j}{r_{ij}} \\ \sum_{j=1}^N V'_j q_j &= k_e \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{i=1 \neq j}^N \frac{q'_i q_j}{r_{ij}} \end{aligned} \tag{103}$$

These equations demonstrate that

$$\sum_{j=1}^N V_j q'_j = \sum_{j=1}^N V'_j q_j \tag{104}$$

which is known as the *Green's Theorem*^{15,12}.

That theorem can be formulated for a system of conductors each at a constant potential V_1, V_2, \dots, V_N and with charges Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_N . Then, if we change their charges to Q'_1, Q'_2, \dots, Q'_N , which correspond to potentials V'_1, V'_2, \dots, V'_N , we obtain

$$\sum_{j=1}^N V_j Q'_j = \sum_{j=1}^N V'_j Q_j \tag{105}$$

C. The Poisson-Boltzmann Model

The Poisson-Boltzmann equation was described in these references^{31,32}. In the Poisson-Boltzmann approach³³, all the molecular atoms are considered explicitly as particles with partial point charges at the atomic positions, and the dielectric constant of the molecule itself is often considered to be low, typically in the range 1-2.

Let us consider first a homogeneous medium with dielectric constant and the external charges are present (i.e., $\rho \neq 0$), for example a molecule is immersed in the gas phase:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho(\mathbf{r}) \tag{106}$$

which leads to the so-called Poisson equation

$$\varepsilon \nabla \cdot (\nabla V(\mathbf{r})) = -\frac{\rho(\mathbf{r})}{\varepsilon_0} \tag{107}$$

In the general case of the nonhomogeneous medium, the polarised charges created at the dielectric boundaries must be taken into account as well, and:

$$\nabla \cdot (\varepsilon(\mathbf{r}) \nabla V(\mathbf{r})) = -\frac{\rho(\mathbf{r})}{\varepsilon_0} \tag{108}$$

where ρ is the distribution of the molecule fixed charge density.

The simplest numerical method for solving field problems is the finite difference method. In this method a regular rectangular mesh is superimposed upon the problem. The real continuous variation of potential with position is then approximated by the values of the potential at the intersections of the mesh lines. Figure 15 shows a small section of a three-dimensional mesh with a spacing h in each direction and the electrostatic potentials at the mesh points.

To find an approximate relationship between the potentials shown, we apply Gauss's law to the surfaces shown by the cubical volume in Figure 15³⁴.

Fig. 15. A three-dimensional mesh with a spacing h in each direction and the electrostatic potentials at the mesh points.

The following system of equations is obtained in three-dimensions:

$$\begin{aligned} &\varepsilon_{i-1,j,k}^x (V_{i,j,k} - V_{i-1,j,k}) + \varepsilon_{i,j,k}^x (V_{i,j,k} - V_{i+1,j,k}) \\ &+ \varepsilon_{i,j-1,k}^y (V_{i,j,k} - V_{i,j-1,k}) + \varepsilon_{i,j,k}^y (V_{i,j,k} - V_{i,j+1,k}) \\ &+ \varepsilon_{i,j,k-1}^z (V_{i,j,k} - V_{i,j,k-1}) + \varepsilon_{i,j,k}^z (V_{i,j,k} - V_{i,j,k+1}) \\ &= \frac{q_{i,j,k}}{h\varepsilon_0} \end{aligned} \quad (109)$$

where i , j , and k are indices along x , y , and z axes, respectively. Furthermore, $\varepsilon_{i,j,k}^x$ is the dielectric constant between the grid points (i, j, k) and $(i + 1, j, k)$, $\varepsilon_{i,j,k}^y$ is the dielectric constant between the grid points (i, j, k) and $(i, j + 1, k)$, and $\varepsilon_{i,j,k}^z$ is the dielectric constant between the grid points (i, j, k) and $(i, j, k + 1)$. $q_{i,j,k}$ is the charge at the grid point (i, j, k) . If the medium is homogeneous with constant dielectric constant of ε , then

$$\begin{aligned} V_{i,j,k} &= \frac{q_{i,j,k}}{6h\varepsilon\varepsilon_0} \\ &+ \frac{1}{6} [V_{i-1,j,k} + V_{i+1,j,k} + V_{i,j-1,k} + V_{i,j+1,k} \\ &+ V_{i,j,k-1} + V_{i,j,k+1}] \end{aligned} \quad (110)$$

From this equation to obtain an estimate of $V_{i,j,k}$ as a function electrostatic potentials in the neighbouring grid points. Because the errors in four potentials cancel each other out to some extent, and because the resulting error is divided by 6, the error in the value of $V_{i,j,k}$ is normally less than the errors in potentials used to calculate it.

In general, the following matrix form of the linear system of equations given by Eq. 109 can be obtained:

$$\mathbf{AV} = \mathbf{Q} \quad (111)$$

where \mathbf{A} is the matrix of the dielectric constants between each grid points and in each direction, \mathbf{V} is the column vector of the grid points potential, and \mathbf{Q} is free charge column vector at each grid point. From solving the Poisson-Boltzmann equation (see Eq. 111), the electrostatic potential, $V(\mathbf{r})$, will be obtained at any point \mathbf{r} in space. Moreover, the gradient of the electrostatic potential can give the electric field, $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}) = -\nabla V(\mathbf{r})$.

The first electrostatic models were formulated in Refs.^{35,36,37,38,39,40}. All these models use either the Poisson-Boltzmann equation or its linear approximation, and hence they were characterised by high accuracy. Initially, the models used simple shape molecular models, such as spheres for proteins and rods for DNA. The models improved by developing methods for solving the Poisson-Boltzmann equation for any arbitrary shape using the finite difference algorithm in software, such as DelPhi, Grasp, and UHBD, and APBS^{41,42,43,44}.

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